

Invocation: <code>spatch ...</code>	description	requires
<code>... --parse-cocci a.cocci</code>	do a semantic patch parse check	
<code>... --parse-c a.c</code>	do a C source file parse check	
<code>... --parse-c++ a.cpp</code>	do a C++ source file parse check	
<code>... a.cocci directory</code>	patch a <i>directory</i>	
<code>... --sp-file a.cocci a.c</code>	get C patch of a.c	
<code>... --sp-file a.cocci a.cpp</code>	get C++ patch of a.cpp	a.cocci begins with <code>#spatch --c++</code>
<code>... --test a</code>	get C patch of a.c	
<code>... --test a</code>	get C++ patch of a.cpp	a.cocci begins with <code>#spatch --c++</code>

```

1 #spatch command line options
2 @rulename ...@
3 metavariabletype v;
4 other metadeclarations
5 @@
6 rule body provides context and
  references metavariables
7 - minus code
  context usually optional
8 + plus code
  context usually optional
9 ++ multiple insertion
    
```

```

1 @initialize:python@ @@
2 python code executed once
3 @r1@
4 metavariabletype s;
5 @@
6 SmPL code referencing s
7 @script: python r2@
8 s << r1.s; // inherit s from r1
9 @@
10 python code referencing s
11 @finalize:python@ @@
12 python code executed once
    
```

```

1 // a semantic patch file
2 @rule1@
3 metavariabletype v;
4 @@
5 * <- special match-only line
  ... <- "ellipses" or "dots"
6 @rule2@
7 metavariabletype rule1.v;
8 @@
9
10 v is inherited and usable
    
```

```

1 @@ @@
2 (
3     first pattern to match
4     & // conjunction of patterns
5     second pattern to match
6     + max one insert per construct
7 ) // changes only within (...)
    
```

```

1 @@ @@
2 (
3     - first match and/or change
4     | // disjunction of patterns
5     - second match and/or change
6 ) // changes only within (...)
    
```

```

1 @rule1@ @@
2 may match or not match
3 @rule2 depends on rule1@ @@
4 matches if rule1 matches
5 @rule3 depends on !rule1@ @@
6 matches if rule1 does not
    
```

```

1 @rulename rulekind@ @@
2 rule affected by rulekind
    
```

```

1 @@
2 statement S; // or other
3 @@
4 ... when != S // constraint
5 ... when any // greedy dots
6 <+... required match ...+>
7 <... optional match ...>
    
```

```

1 #include "file.cocci"
2 @@
3 // comment (ignored)
4 @@
5 + 0 // after // are comments
6 - 0 // need rule even if
7 // #include'ing rules
    
```

metavariabletype v	no v identifier, but token	v={a,...} or v!={a,...}	v=~regexp	list[n={N...M}] v	simply removable (-v)	is top-level	notes
attribute name	✓						implicit semantic patch-wide scope; on types, identifiers and function headers;
constant		✓	✓				
declaration					✓		given identifier I and declaration D, usable as I@D
expression		✓		✓			given expression E and statement E, usable as E@S
field				✓			
format			✓	✓			
function			✓			✓	declarations only
identifier		✓	✓	✓			also: fresh identifier j=v##"_new", identifier list in macro definitions
idexpression							
local idexpression							e.g. local idexpression type i
global idexpression						✓	e.g. global idexpression i
assignment operator		✓					
binary operator		✓					replacing operator token with metavariable may invalidate isomorphisms
parameter				✓			can produce expression list EL from parameter list PL, e.g. PL@EL
position							in rules as @p after any token
pragmainfo			✓				only regexp match
statement				✓	✓		
symbol	✓						implicit semantic patch-wide scope
type		✓	✓				
typedef	✓						implicit semantic patch-wide scope

@ rulekind@	implicit	match requirement	error	meaning
expression	✓	token must also be expression	invalid minus	non simply removable (need context)
identifier	✗	any token (also in declaration)	already tagged token	conflicting changes overlap
forall	in ...	between dots, all paths must match	parse error	trying matching more top-level things?
exists	in * lines	one matching path suffices	none, but no patch	does the source fully parse?
disable all	✗	no isomorphisms (see --iso-limit 0)	no available token to attach	+ just outside a & or construct